

Assessment of long COVID symptoms and post-COVID quality of life in youth

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Abstract

Background: The global prevalence of lengthy COVID among youth remains unknown, demanding a thorough investigation of symptoms and post-COVID quality of life. The purpose of this study was to identify these symptoms and assess their quality of life.

Methods: A census approach was used to poll 264 people in Bengaluru, India. Demographic information, COVID symptoms, and SF-36 questionnaire responses were gathered. Using ICD-10-CM codes, symptoms were detected, and statistical analyses were done.

Results: Long COVID symptoms were found in 43.2% of subjects, with 23.5% experiencing Ongoing COVID-19 Symptoms (OCS) and 15.9% experiencing post-COVID-19 Syndrome (PCS). Gender differences in symptom patterns were discovered. Males had a higher incidence of pain ($p = .0005$), whereas females had a higher incidence of hair loss ($p = 0.00009$), headaches ($p = 0.02$), and irregular periods (16.2%). The duration of symptoms ranged from less than one month (46.6%) to more than five months (10.2%). In the Quality-of-Life assessment, mental health was the most affected domain.

Conclusion: This study found a considerable prevalence of extended COVID in youth that lasted more than 5 months after recovery. The impact on quality of life is significant, highlighting the critical need for standardized post-COVID care strategies. The findings of this study contribute to a better knowledge of the changing landscape of extended COVID, suggesting sustained attention and specific therapies.

Keywords: COVID-19, Long-term COVID, Post COVID-19 syndrome, Post-acute sequelae of COVID-19, COVID recovery, Youth, India.

Introduction

The preface of the new severe acute respiratory pattern coronavirus 2 (SARS- CoV- 2) has redounded in the global spread of COVID- 19. COVID- 19 is a complex sickness that affects not only the respiratory tract but also other organ systems (1). It's

characterized by common symptoms similar as fever, cough, and frazzle. Headache, diarrhea, rashes, and sore throat are smaller common symptoms. While numerous people witness mild to severe respiratory illness and recover without treatment, there is a small chance of developing severe sickness that necessitates medical attention (2).

COVID- 19 has a global risk of roughly 634 million verified cases as of November 28, 2022, with close to 6 million losses (3). According to WHO epidemiological data, around 15 of COVID- 19 cases have severe airway complaint, and 5 suffer critical sickness taking mechanical ventilation. roughly 80 of cases have no or mild to moderate symptoms (4). The COVID- 19 epidemic has sparked a global health exigency, caused wide dislocations and aggravating pre-existing injuries. The impact of the extremity varies greatly by age group, with youthful people, particularly vulnerable youth, suffering considerable obstacles in academy, work, internal health, and disposable cash. To avoid the worsening of intergenerational injuries, governments must address the special conditions of the youth population as they transition from critical extremity operation to recovery measures (5).

According to 2011 Census data, India has roughly 233 million youthful people. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines the ' Youth' population in the South- East Asia Region as those aged 15 to 24, italicizing the significance of distinguishing this group from ' Adolescents' (10- 19 times) and ' Young People' (10- 24 times) (6). The acute phase of COVID- 19 infection can extend up to 4 weeks after infection. Still, a significant proportion of people may continue to have symptoms after the acute phase has passed, performing in " long COVID" (1).

NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence) recommendations contain the ensuing delineations to identify and diagnose the long- term goods of COVID- 19 (7):

- Acute COVID- 19 – “Signs and symptoms of COVID - 19 for over to 4 weeks.”
- Ongoing characteristic COVID- 19 – “Signs and symptoms of COVID - 19 from 4 weeks up to 12 weeks.”
- Post-COVID-19 pattern – “Signs and symptoms that develop during or after an infection harmonious with COVID - 19, continue for further than 12 weeks and aren't explained by an indispensable opinion. It generally presents clusters of symptoms, frequently lapping, which can change and change over time and can affect any system in the body. Post - COVID - 19 pattern may be considered before 12 weeks while the possibility of an indispensable beginning complaint is also being assessed.”
- “In addition to the clinical case delineations, the term ‘long COVID’ is generally used to describe signs and symptoms that continue or develop after acute COVID - 19. It includes both ongoing characteristic COVID - 19 (from 4 to 12 weeks) and post - COVID - 19 pattern (12 weeks or further).”

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), " long COVID is astronomically defined as signs, symptoms, and conditions that continue or develop after acute COVID- 19 infection" (8).

Cases suffering from long- term COVID report significant multi-systemic damage and disability. Indeed, seven months after their original opinion, numerous individuals hadn't entirely recovered and were unfit to renew their former situations of exertion. They're still dealing with a significant burden of symptoms that are affecting their quality of life (9). The most common signs and symptoms of acute COVID- 19 are breathlessness, coughing, casket miserliness, casket pain, prostration, fever, headache, disturbed sleep, abdominal discomfort, diarrhea, skin rashes, common pain, loss of taste or smell, disorientation, and hair loss. While current public guidelines recommend introductory characteristic treatments, substantiation for medicinal remedy that address the illness itself is shy (7).

Despite rising knowledge of the substantial health difficulties that impact those recovering from COVID- 19, the long- term consequences, particularly among youthful people, remain largely understood. The population of youth are constantly included as groups in studies, performing inadequate data on the youth population with lengthy COVID- 19 and conceivably undervaluing the inflexibility of new post-COVID diseases. Given the cerebral and social consequences of lengthy COVID, especially during the transition to majority, studying this group is critical.

Understanding the clinical impact of prolonged COVID on the juvenile population is critical for relating those at threat, determining illness duration, and directly depicting the complaint's course. This understanding is critical for efficiently fastening prospective treatments and addressing the unique issues endured by youth with extended COVID.

Methods

Sample Size Estimation

The computation was inspired by a pilot study with a sample size of 30 patients, 24 of whom had long COVID symptoms (80% population proportion). The projected sample size was 283, based on the "Cochran formula" with z value (1.96 for a 95% confidence interval), population proportion (80% based on pilot research), margin of error (5%), and 15% non-responsive participants. Sample population flowchart is shown in Figure 1.

Materials and methods

This was an observational study in Bengaluru, Karnataka, with 264 individuals chosen using specified inclusion/exclusion criteria and the census method based on disease prevalence estimates. Individuals who had tested positive for COVID-19 once and were currently COVID-19 negative, aged 18 to 24 years, and gave their consent were included, while those with a history of mental illness and those who tested positive more than once were excluded.

A questionnaire including demographic variables such as age, gender, vaccination status, occupation, and social habits, probable post-COVID-19 symptoms according to the 2023 ICD-10-CM Codes, and the duration of the symptoms was sent online via Google forms. The goal of the study was explained to the participants, and their agreement was obtained. The SF-36 (RAND 36-Item Health Survey Instrument) questionnaire was used in conjunction with the questionnaire on demographic characteristics (10). It is a collection of general, consistent, and simple quality-of-life measurements. These measures, which rely on patient self-reporting, are frequently used to assess health-related Quality of Life (HRQOL). It addresses eight health domains: physical functioning, role limitation owing to physical health, role limitation due to emotional problems, energy/fatigue, emotional well-being, social functioning, pain, and overall health.

The collected data was entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and suitable descriptive and statistical analysis was performed. The Chi square test was used to determine the relationship between symptoms and gender, and the Two-Factor ANOVA test with no replication was used to determine the relationship between symptom duration and gender.

This research was carried out in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration's standards. The Acharya & BM Reddy College of Pharmacy's Ethics Committee approved the study on March 23, 2022. All individual participants in the study gave their informed consent.

Results

264 people from Bengaluru, Karnataka, India, took part in the study. The average age of the participants was 22.37 ± 3.11 . There were 116 (44%) male participants and 148 (56%) female participants. Out of the 264 individuals, 26% had not been vaccinated, 20% had received a single dose of vaccination, and 54% had received both doses of the vaccine. Among the entire number of subjects, 91% received Covishield, 7% received Covaxin, and just 2% received Sputnik. Many participants, 78%, were students, 18% were employed, and 3% were jobless. 11.7% of participants had previously used alcohol, 12.1% were smokers, 6% had quit using alcohol, and 3% had stopped smoking (Table 1).

The most prevalent symptom reported during COVID-19 recovery was weakness (56.4%), followed by cough (52.7%), fever (49.2%), headache (44.7%), fatigue (43.9%), and shortness of breath (36.7%). Visual disturbance was seen in 0.8% of cases, followed by skin rashes in 1.5%, mobility impairment in 1.5%, abdominal pain in 4.9%, and nausea and vomiting in 9.8% (Figure 2).

Cough was the most prevalent symptom seen in 52.6% of male participants, followed by weakness in 52.6%, fever in 52.6%, weariness in 37.9%, shortness of breath in 37.1%, and headache in 37.1%. Skin rash was observed in 0.9%, mobility limitation in 1.7%, abdominal pain in 5.2%, chest pain in 7.8%, and nausea and vomiting in 7.8%. The most prevalent symptoms reported among the female participants in the study were weakness in 59.5%, cough in 52.7%, headache in 50.7%, fatigue in 48.6%, fever in 46.6%, and hair loss in 39.2%. While vision disturbance was detected in 1.4%, mobility impairment was seen in 1.4%, skin rashes were shown in 2%, stomach pain was seen in 4.7%, and pain was seen in 7.4% (Figure 3).

Duration of symptoms in participants

Among the 264 individuals in the study, the following symptom durations were reported: 46.6% for less than one month, 15.2% for 1-2 months, 8.3% for 2-3 months, 5.7% for 3-4 months, 3.8% for 4-5 months, and 10.2% for more than 5 months (Figure 4).

Association between symptoms and gender

The Chi square test was used to evaluate the relationship between symptoms and gender. Males suffered much higher pain than females ($P = 0.0005$), although weight loss ($P = 0.08$) was inconsequential.

Notably, males experienced significantly less hair loss ($P = 0.00009$) and headache ($P = 0.02$) than females, with both findings reaching significance at $p < 0.05$. Approximately 16.2% of ladies had irregular periods.

In terms of cognitive symptoms, males reported less sleep disturbance ($P = 0.65$) and less concentration ($P = 0.83$) than females. Furthermore, males had lower levels of dizziness ($P = 0.1$), fatigue ($P = 0.08$), weakness ($P = 0.26$), chest tightness ($P = 0.27$), chest pain ($P = 0.24$), reduced appetite ($P = 0.24$), and nausea & vomiting ($P = 0.31$) than females, albeit this was not statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

These findings highlight the existence of gender differences in symptom expression, with certain symptoms exhibiting statistically significant relationships while others did not exceed the specified significance level. The thorough examination of these correlations provides a more complete knowledge of the interplay between gender and symptomatology in the group investigated.

Association between symptom duration and gender

A Two-Factor ANOVA test with no replication was used to assess the relationship between symptom duration and gender. 0.000339 was determined as the p -value. The discovery was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Quality of life

The mean scores for physical components: physical functioning, role limitation due to physical health, pain, and general health, on the SF-36 questionnaire were 76.34 ± 4.93 , 69.58 ± 10.73 , 78.42 ± 4.96 , and 60.12 ± 5.92 , respectively (Table 2). The mean scores for the mental components: role limitation owing to emotional issues, energy, emotional well-being, and social functioning, were 75.75 ± 11.14 , 54.33 ± 4.84 , 55.83 ± 3.04 , and 70.90 ± 6.39 , respectively (Table 3). The overall averages for the physical component were 71.11 ± 8.24 and 64.20 ± 10.73 for the mental component. (Table 4).

Males had mean scores of 80.66 9.86, 81.48 16.71, 84.75 8.09, and 67.48 9.84 for physical components, whereas females had scores of 74.05 5.66, 64.93 11.31, 75.47 4.86, and 56.51 4.73 (Figure 4). Males had mean scores of 86.68 11.50, 57.97 6.22, 57.57 6.65, and 77.07 8.14, while females had scores of 70.76 12.91, 52.28 4.59, 54.7 2.88, and 67.7 6.46 (Figure 5).

The overall average for the physical component in males was 78.59 7.61, and 67.74 8.82 in females (Figures 5 and 6), while the average for the mental

component in males was 69.82 14.46, and 61.36 9.22 in females.

Discussion

According to the findings of this study, a considerable percentage of patients have lengthy COVID symptoms. Even after five months of recuperation, symptoms may persist, however this varies from person to person. Long COVID symptoms were reported by 43.2% of participants. In the ongoing COVID-19 symptoms (OCS) phase, 23.5% were recorded, and 15.9% were recorded in the post-COVID-19 syndrome (PCS) phase, which is consistent with the study conducted by Petersen and colleagues (11), which shows the persistence of symptoms even after a mean of 125 days after symptoms onset.

After recovery, the most prevalent symptom was weakness (56.4%), followed by cough (52.7%), fever (49.2%), headache (44.7%), weariness (43.9%), and shortness of breath (36.7%). While visual disturbance (0.8%) was the least common symptom observed, it was followed by skin rashes (1.5%), mobility impairment (1.5%), and abdominal pain (4.9%), which is consistent with a study conducted by Alkodaymi and colleagues (12), which identifies the prevalence of persistent symptoms and signs in patients 12 weeks after acute COVID-19.

Females exhibited a higher rate of hair loss and headache than males, which is consistent with the findings of Yadav and colleagues (13), who identified hair fall as a long COVID symptom.

Females endured irregular periods as well.

Females experienced more cognitive symptoms such as difficulty concentrating and sleep disturbance when compared to men, which is consistent with the findings of studies conducted by Ceban and colleagues (14), and Jennings G and colleagues (1), which show that a significant proportion of individuals experience persistent cognitive impairment. Women were likewise dizzy than men. Men, on the other hand, reported higher degrees of pain and lower levels of exhaustion than women, which is consistent with previous research. Furthermore, men lost more weight than women. The overall reduction in these persons' quality of life affects both the Physical and Mental Components. Importantly, in both genders, the mental component is the most affected domain.

Table 1. Patient characteristics

Characteristics	No. of participants	Percentage %
Age		
18	3	1.1
19	20	7.57
20	28	10.6
21	27	10.2
22	39	14.7
23	39	14.7
24	108	40.9
Total	264	
Gender		
Male	116	44
Female	148	56
Total	264	
Vaccination before COVID-19?		
No	68	26
1 st Dose	53	20
2 nd Dose	143	54
Total	264	
Vaccine taken		
Covishield	240	91
Covaxin	19	7
Sputnik	5	2
Total	264	
Occupation		
Student	206	78
Employed	48	18
Unemployed	8	3
Total	264	
Social Habits		
Alcohol	31	12
Smoking	32	12
None	210	80
Stopped using alcohol	15	6
Stopped smoking	8	3
Total	264	

Table 2. Physical component summary

Scale	Mean	SD
Physical functioning	75.74	24.92
Role limitation due to physical health	72.30	35.36
Pain	78.89	21.54
General health	61.71	17.37

Table 3. Mental component summary

Scale	Mean	SD
Role limitation due to emotional problems	76.74	35.37
Energy/fatigue	55.98	14.55
Emotional well-being	56.86	15.47
Social functioning	70.46	21.47

Table 4. Both physical and mental component summary

Scale	Mean	SD
Physical component summary	71.11	8.24
Mental component summary	64.20	10.73
Total average	67.65	4.88

Figure 1. Sample population flowchart

Figure 2. Distribution of observed symptoms in participants

Figure 3. Distribution of observed symptoms by gender

Figure 4. Duration of symptoms in the participants

Figure 5. Distribution of physical components among gender

Figure 6. Distribution of mental components among gender

The study's findings underscore the need of extended COVID. This lengthy symptom persistence post-COVID-19 emphasizes the potentially prolonged nature of the disease's aftermath, emphasizing the need for comprehensive post-COVID therapy.

Understanding both COVID-19 and long COVID symptoms is critical for understanding the condition, especially given the changing climate, rising urbanization, and lifestyle choices that contribute to an increased risk of respiratory issues and subsequent complications. To successfully manage developing health concerns, prevent further symptom prolongation, and improve overall quality of life, a thorough and consistent strategy must be established. These findings add to the growing body of information on long COVID, pushing healthcare providers, politicians, and researchers to address the long COVID symptoms that arise as a result of COVID-19 in youth. The study's findings provide important insights for the development of treatment strategies targeted at preventing symptoms from worsening and improving overall quality of life. Furthermore, the study highlights the need for additional research into the prevalence of long COVID symptoms in the current scenario, despite the fact that the number of COVID-positive individuals has significantly decreased.

The study has potential limitations (1). The study is retrospective in nature, and it has inherent limitations that could lead to bias and confounding (2). Due to practical limits, not all relevant illness information

could be acquired, which would have provided additional value to the study (2). Individual psychological aspects were not explicitly examined in the study, resulting in a gap in their understanding of sickness (3). Because the questionnaire was delivered via an online platform, subjectivity in participants' understanding of the questionnaire could not be assessed (4). Because the data was gathered from a small number of participants in Bengaluru, it may not be a genuine representation of patterns across the city.

Conclusion

As the world grapples with the long-term consequences of the COVID-19 epidemic, our findings highlight the importance of comprehensive post-COVID treatment and a standardized strategy to address developing health concerns, reduce symptom prolonging, and improve overall well-being. Despite the fact that the number of active cases has significantly decreased, this study calls for continued vigilance and research efforts to understand the evolving landscape of post-COVID sequelae, particularly among the youth population, and to develop effective strategies for timely and tailored interventions.

Author's Contribution

Mohammed Wasim played an important role in the research. He was in charge of developing the study's concept and design, as well as collecting and analyzing data and interpreting the results. Mr. Wasim also wrote the manuscript. Sheethal Kuriakose, the study's advisor, made significant contributions. Her expertise in clinical trials and pharmacovigilance contributed in the text's essential modifications for substantial intellectual substance, such as statistical analysis. Other pharmacy practice faculties and the guide extensively evaluated and approved the manuscript, displaying their joint input and endorsement.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interest.

References

- Jennings, G., Monaghan, A., Xue, F., Mockler, D., Romero-Ortuño, R. A systematic review of persistent symptoms and residual abnormal functioning following acute COVID-19: Ongoing symptomatic phase vs. Post COVID-19 syndrome. *J Clin Med* 2021;10(24):5913.
- World Health Organization. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19). 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus>.
- World Health Organization. WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) dashboard/Cases. 2023. Available from: <https://COVID19.who.int/>
- Lemhöfer, C., Sturm, C., Loudovici-Krug, D., Best, N., Gutenbrunner, C. The impact of Post-COVID-Syndrome on functioning - results from a community survey in patients after mild and moderate SARS-CoV-2-infections in Germany. *J Occup Med Toxicol* 2021;16(1):45.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Youth and COVID-19: Response, recovery and resilience. 2020. Available from: <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/youth-and-covid-19-response-recovery-and-resilience-c40e61c6/#section-d1e113>.
- World Health Organization. Health topics/Adolescent health. 2022. Available from: <https://www.who.int/southeastasia/health-topics/adolescent-health>.
- Recommendations/COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing the long-term effects of COVID-19/Guidance/NICE. 2021. Available from: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng188/chapter/Recommendations>.
- CDC. Long COVID or post-COVID conditions. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2023. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/long-term-effects/index.html>.
- Davis, H.E., Assaf, G.S., McCorkell, L., Wei, H., Low, R.J., Re'em, Y., et al. Characterizing long COVID in an international cohort: 7 months of symptoms and their impact. *EClinicalMedicin*. 2021;38:101019.
- Research and Development (RAND). 36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36). 2022. Available from: https://www.rand.org/health-care/surveys_tools/mos/36-item-short-form.html.
- Petersen, M.S., Kristiansen, M.F., Hanusson, K.D., Danielsen, M.E., Steig, B.A., Gaini, S., et al. Long COVID in the Faroe Islands: A longitudinal study among nonhospitalized patients. *Clin Infect Dis* 2021;73(11):e4058–e4063.
- Alkodaymi, M.S., Omrani, O.A., Fawzy, N.A., Shaar, B.A., Almamlouk, A., Riaz, M., et al. Prevalence of post-acute COVID-19 syndrome symptoms at different follow-up periods: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2022;28(5):657–66.

13. Yadav, A.K., Mukherjee, G., Vasisht, K., Bobdey, S. Long COVID among moderate to severe COVID-19 cases in India during second wave of COVID-19. *Asia Pac J Public Health*. 2022; 34(8):846-848.
14. Ceban, F., Ling, S., Lui, L.M.W., Lee, Y., Gill, H., Teopiz, K.M., et al. Fatigue and cognitive impairment in Post COVID-19 Syndrome: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brain Behav Immun* 2022; 101:93–135.